

21 EPS (TB). The accelerated electron transfer further increased enzyme activity and the
22 metabolic rate of microorganisms. This study indicates that weak electrical stimulation could
23 improve activities of biological enzymes to enhance denitrification efficiency.

24 **Keywords:** Weak electrical stimulation; Denitrification; Enzyme activity; EPS; Electron
25 transfer

26 **1. Introduction**

27 Increasingly prominent nitrogen pollution of water bodies poses a serious threat to
28 human health and ecological functions[1, 2]. Biological nitrogen removal has become one of
29 the cost-effective methods for nitrogen removal because of its high efficiency and low cost.
30 Biological denitrification is completed by aerobic nitrification ($\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}\text{---}\text{NO}_2^-\text{-N}\text{---}\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$)
31 and anoxic denitrification ($\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}\text{---}\text{NO}_2^-\text{-N}\text{---}\text{N}_2$) using aerobic nitrification bacteria and
32 denitrification bacteria respectively[3]. However, in practical wastewater applications, when
33 the C/N (COD/TN) ratio of wastewater is low, the microorganisms will not be able to perform
34 efficient denitrification due to insufficient carbon source[4]. To solve this issue, researchers
35 have combined microbial fuel cells (MFC) with denitrification as an alternative to additional
36 dosage of carbon sources such as methanol and acetate for the treatment of low C/N
37 wastewater[5, 6]. In this case nitrate and nitrite acted as electron acceptors in the cathode
38 chamber of MFC. Under the catalytic action of denitrifying microorganisms, the cathode
39 electrode electrons could be used for electrochemical denitrification directly while energy
40 could be recovered[7, 8]. Thus in recent years, studies using voltages lower than the
41 hydrolysis voltage (1.23V) to promote microbial processes have attracted wide attention[9].

42 Studies have shown that electrical stimulation at constant potential shortens the duration
 43 of the growth arrest period of denitrifying bacteria cells and significantly increases the
 44 denitrification efficiency[10]. At the same time, microbial activity increases with current
 45 density[11]. Higher current intensity promotes denitrification at surface of the MFC cathode,
 46 increasing denitrifying bacteria activity, and leading to further denitrification[12].When the
 47 current intensity exceeds a certain range, it also has an inhibitory effect on microbial activity,
 48 which affects the denitrification reaction[13]. Denitrification is carried out gradually by
 49 specific enzymes as shown in equations 1-4.

51 Wang et al.[14] investigated the effect of carbon nanotubes on the denitrification
 52 performance of the alkali-producing gene and found that denitrification could be promoted by
 53 increasing the activity of NAR, NIR and nitric oxide synthase (NOS). This promotion is
 54 directly responsible for the increased nitrate removal efficiency and reduced N₂O production.
 55 Previous studies have shown that denitrifying enzyme activity is influenced by electron
 56 acceptors[15], C/N[16], pH and other factors[17]. The decrease in C/N ratio affected
 57 synthesis of denitrifying enzymes and hindered the growth of denitrification microorganisms.
 58 Low pH and high H⁺ concentration caused unstable enzyme structure and inhibited the NAR
 59 activity.

60 In this study, we used direct current (DC) power supply to study the effect of weak
 61 electrical stimulation on the denitrification process by adjusting the C/N ratios and weak

62 electrical stimulation intensity, and investigate the pathway of weak electrical stimulation and
63 its effect on denitrification performance from the perspective of denitrifying enzymes.
64 Components of produced gas during denitrification have been detected together with
65 denitrification efficiency analysis of the process. The effect of weak electrical stimulation on
66 microbial metabolism was explored through denitrifying enzyme activity analysis, EPS
67 content detection and distribution profiling. The mechanism of weak electrical stimulation on
68 microbial denitrification enhancement was further proposed, providing a new tool improving
69 denitrification performance under low carbon source water quality conditions.

70 **2. Materials and methods**

71 **2.1 Experimental setup**

72 [Fig.1](#) shows schematic diagram of the experimental setup. The volume of the
73 experimental set-up in this study was 1.2 L. It was divided into a control group (CK, no
74 electrical stimulation set-up) and an experimental group (EG, electrical stimulation set-up).
75 The electrical stimulation voltage values of 0.2 V (0.567mA/cm²), 0.4 V (1.12mA/cm²) and
76 0.6 V (1.74mA/cm²) were selected according to results of our previous study[18]; while the
77 corresponding current intensity was set as the output value of the DC power supply. The
78 experimental electrodes and the usage method are also consistent with the previous study[18].
79 In this study, 200 mL of anaerobic denitrification sludge and 800 mL of artificial wastewater
80 were fed to the reactor in a continuous ascending flow with a hydraulic retention time of 12
81 hours. The C/N ratio was set at two values as 4 (COD and NO₃⁻-N concentrations of 200 and
82 50 mg/L, respectively) and 3 (COD and NO₃⁻-N concentrations of 150 and 50 mg/L,
83 respectively).

84 **Insert Fig. 1. Continuous flow of weak electrically stimulated denitrification schematic**
85 **diagram of the experimental setup**

86 The main components of the low C/N wastewater are shown in [Table 1](#). The components
87 of the concentrated solution of trace elements are 1.61 g/L $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1.5 g/L $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$,
88 0.15 g/L H_3BO_3 , 0.18 g/L KI, 0.12 g/L $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.12 g/L $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.03 g/L
89 $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.06 g/L $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

90 **Insert Table 1. Composition of the artificial simulated wastewater**

91 The anaerobic denitrification sludge was obtained from the East Shanghai Wastewater
92 Treatment Plant (31°16'40.50"N, 121°32'39.99"E) and domesticated using the same
93 conditions as the experimental synthetic wastewater. The sludge was 100% returned and
94 replenished with new sludge every three to five days to maintain a sludge concentration of
95 about 5000 mg/L in the reactor.

96 **2.2 Analytical methods**

97 **2.2.1 Analysis of nitrogenous pollutants**

98 Sludge sampling was carried out every 12 hours. After adjusting the equipment current
99 intensity and/or C/N ratios and other parameters, it needs to be stabilized for 3-5 days before
100 sampling. The concentrations of $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2^-\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ and TN were determined by the
101 nano-reagent photometry, N-(1-naphthyl)-ethylenediamine spectrophotometry, ultraviolet
102 spectrophotometry and potassium persulfate to eliminate ultraviolet spectrophotometric
103 determination respectively.

104 **2.2.2 Gas component detection**

105 Gas production was collected continuously for 7 days at an optimum voltage of 0.2 V to

106 analyze the effect of weak electrical stimulation on the denitrification process. The hydrogen,
107 nitrogen and nitrous oxide were measured by the Shimadzu GC-14B gas chromatograph
108 (Japan), Thermo TRACE 1300 gas chromatograph (USA) and Agilent 6890N gas
109 chromatograph (USA), respectively. The experimental samples were collected using an
110 E-Switch sampling bag, and a 1 mL syringe was used for the measurement. The injection
111 volume of hydrogen, nitrogen and nitrous oxide were 1.0 mL, 0.1 mL and 1.0 mL respectively.
112 A single point calibration was performed using the lowest concentration point when the
113 sample concentration was well below the lowest point of the standard series (The standard
114 curve is shown in [Fig.S1](#)). The measuring conditions are listed as in [Table 2](#).

115 **Insert Table 2. Conditions for determination of hydrogen, nitrogen and nitrous oxide**

116 **2.2.3 Denitrifying enzymes (NAR, NIR) extraction and activity determination**

117 We investigated the effect of weak electrical stimulation on denitrifying microbial
118 activity under weak electrical stimulation by measuring NAR and NIR activities. The mixed
119 liquid suspended solid from different groups was centrifuged at 5000 r for 5 min at 4 °C. The
120 centrifuged precipitate was rinsed with 0.01 M phosphate buffer (PBS) at pH 7.4 for three
121 times, resuspended in 0.01 M PBS buffer at pH 7.4, and sonicated in an ice bath (20 kHz) for
122 5 min. After sonication, the cell suspension was placed in a centrifuge at 12000r for 15 min at
123 4°C, and the supernatant was then taken and stored. The reaction system consisted of 1.0 mL
124 of crude enzyme extract with 0.01 M PBS (pH=7.4), 1.0 mM NaNO₃, 1.0 mM methyl violet
125 gum and 5.0 mM Na₂S₂O₄. The reaction system was placed in a thermostat and shaken for 30
126 min at 30°C, and then the nitrite concentration was measured by an ultraviolet
127 spectrophotometer (UV-2600 Shimadzu, Japan). NAR and NIR enzyme activities were

128 expressed as NO_3^- -N produced or reduced during the reaction ($\mu\text{g NO}_3^-$ -N/min--mg
129 protein)[19].

130 **2.2.4 Analysis of extracellular polymers substances (EPS)**

131 The extracellular polymer substances (EPS) was extracted from the sludge by thermal
132 extraction[20] after filtered through a 0.45 μm membrane to remove the particulate matter and
133 then analyzed qualitatively using a 3D fluorescence spectrometer F-7000 FL (Hitachi, Japan).
134 The excitation wavelength of the 3D fluorescence spectrometer was set from 200 to 420 nm,
135 and the emission wavelength was set from 250 to 550 nm in increments of 2 nm. The slit
136 widths of both excitation and emission were 2.5 nm, and the scanning speed was 12000
137 nm/min. The EPS was also quantified and the protein content in the supernatant of the
138 samples was determined by the Komasa Brilliant Blue method[21].

139 **3. Results and discussion**

140 **3.1 Effect of weak electrical stimulation on denitrification efficiency**

141 [Fig.2](#) shows the variation of NO_3^- -N, NO_2^- -N, NH_4^+ -N and TN concentrations under the
142 influence of different C/N and microbial weak electrical stimulation voltages. By comparing
143 the performances at different voltages in [Fig.2](#), it can be found that the best effect of microbial
144 weak electrical stimulation is at 0.2 V under both C/N ratios of 3 and 4. The total nitrogen and
145 nitrate in the EG group with the C/N ratio of 3 decreased to about 20 mg/L and 17 mg/L at a
146 weak stimulation voltage of 0.2 V, while the total nitrogen and nitrate in the CK group
147 decreased to about 24 mg/L and 20 mg/L, respectively. The removal rates of total nitrogen
148 and nitrate in the EG group increased both by 8% compared with those in the CK group
149 ([Fig.2a, b](#)). When the microbial weak electrical stimulation voltage was 0.4 V, there was little

150 difference between the degradation in the CK group and the EG group; while at the weak
151 electrical stimulation voltage of 0.6 V, the nitrate removal rate in the EG group was lower
152 than that in the CK group. It could be speculated that under relatively low carbon source
153 conditions, the degradation effect may be negatively correlated with an increase in the weak
154 electrical stimulation, with 0.6 V corresponding to a weak electrical stimulation intensity that
155 is detrimental to microbial metabolisms. The above results are comparable to the results of
156 Prošňanský et al.[22]. The best effect was obtained when the current density was 0.27
157 mA/cm², and there was no difference between the experimental group and the control group
158 when the current density is 0.467 mA/cm². The denitrification rate decreased when the current
159 density was greater than 1.2 mA/cm², and when the current density exceeded 2 mA/cm², the
160 denitrification effect decreased significantly.

161 **Insert Fig.2 Removal effect and pH change of weakly electrically stimulated**
162 **denitrification continuous flow experiment;(a)TN, (b)NO₃⁻-N, (c) NO₂⁻-N , (d)**
163 **NH₄⁺-N,(e)pH**

164 Under the condition of an influent C/N of 4, the total nitrogen and nitrate could be
165 reduced to about 11 mg/L and 9 mg/L in the EG group and about 22 mg/L and 18 mg/L in the
166 CK group; meanwhile, the total nitrogen and nitrate removal rates in the EG group were
167 improved by about 12% and 20%, respectively, compared with the CK group (Fig.2a, b).
168 Microbial heterotrophic denitrification using organic matter or autotrophic denitrification
169 using hydrogen are both alkali-producing processes, and the reduction of 1 mg of nitrate can
170 simultaneously produce 3.57 mg of alkalinity. As shown in Fig.2e, the alkalinity of the EG
171 effluent was higher than that of the CK effluent, indicating that weak electrical stimulation

172 has a positive effect on the denitrification process.

173 The variation curves of nitrite nitrogen and ammonia nitrogen in Fig. 2 c, d showed that
174 nitrite nitrogen in the effluent of the EG group was lower than that of the CK group under the
175 effect of weak electrical stimulation at 0.2 V, 0.4 V and 0.6 V, while the concentration of
176 ammonia nitrogen showed an opposite trend. There are two main pathways of biological
177 nitrogen cycling associated with nitrate in nature, in addition to biological denitrification, and
178 the dissimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonium (DNRA)[23].

180 NH_4^+ -N is the end product of the DNRA process, and it can be demonstrated from Fig.2d
181 that there was an accumulation of NH_4^+ -N in the EG group under weak electrical stimulation,
182 partly because the high ammonia nitrogen content of the synthetic water after sludge dilution
183 and partly because DNRA was presumed to have occurred during denitrification. Meanwhile,
184 the degree of accumulation in the EG group increased with the increase of voltage compared
185 to the CK group, indicating that electrical stimulation accelerated the DNRA process.
186 According to Fig.4, the NIR activity of the EG group was enhanced by weak electrical
187 stimulation, which reduced the accumulation of nitrite due to insufficient carbon source.

188 The above results showed that the effect of weak microbial electrical stimulation on
189 nitrate-containing wastewater was largely positive at different voltages and C/N ratios. the
190 highest removal efficiencies for both TN and nitrate nitrogen were obtained at 0.2 V. the
191 nitrite nitrogen content was significantly higher in the CK group than in the EG group.

192 **3.2 Variation of gas production & compositions under weak electric stimulation**

193 When the denitrification efficiency reached the highest value with a weak electrical

194 stimulus of 0.2V, we collected gas production fractions from the EG group at 0.2V for
195 comparison with the CK group. Gas production during the denitrification process varies under
196 different C/N conditions[24]. Fig.3a,b and c demonstrated H₂, N₂ and N₂O contents of the
197 denitrification gas at the optimal weak electrical stimulation intensity (0.2 V) for C/N ratios of
198 3 and 4. The percentage of H₂ content in the gas produced by both EG and CK groups was at
199 a lower level at C/N ratios of 3 and 4, but percentage of H₂ content in the EG group increased
200 compared to the CK group, presumably because the accelerated electron transfer by the
201 applied voltage promoted the activity of hydrogen-producing bacteria. It is generally believed
202 that autotrophic denitrifying microorganisms use the H₂ produced by cathode electrolysis as
203 an electron supply. H₂ can replace organic carbon as an electron donor, relieving the challenge
204 of insufficient carbon source, and promoting denitrification, as shown in Fig.2. The N₂
205 content in the produced gas was lower in the EG group than in the CK group since the
206 microbial activity of N₂O reductase synthesis was probably inhibited by DOC depletion in the
207 EG group at the late stage of denitrification due to the low carbon source, while the anaerobic
208 ammonia oxidation process could exist in the CK group at the same time, and NH₄⁺ replaced
209 DOC as an electron donor to undergo redox reactions with NO₂⁻, and then more N₂ was
210 produced[25].

211 **Insert Fig.3 Denitrification gas production at the optimal weak electrical stimulation**
212 **intensity of 0.2 V; (a) H₂, (b) N₂,(c) N₂O**

213 It was controversial that when the C/N ratio is different, the N₂O content changes in the
214 opposite trend. At a C/N ratio of 3, it was evident that lower levels of N₂O were produced
215 with the 0.2 V weak electrical stimulation, representing a more complete denitrification

216 process. In contrast, at a C/N ratio of 4, the N₂O production was higher with 0.2 V weak
217 electrical stimulation. This may be partly due to the accumulation of nitrite (Fig. 2c), which
218 leads to the production of N₂O[26], and partly due to the weak electrical stimulation, which
219 enhances the denitrifying enzyme activity. Denitrification by microorganisms consists of
220 several stages, such as NO₃⁻→NO₂⁻→NO→N₂O→N₂. The microorganisms and related
221 enzymes NAR, NIR, NOR and N₂OR in each stage are different, so are the effects of weak
222 electrical stimulation on the activities of different microorganisms and enzymes. Interactions
223 between enzymes can affect the electron supply in endogenous denitrification. Restricted
224 electron supply will lead to a significant accumulation of N₂O in the denitrification phase[27].
225 According to the microbial community detection and analysis results (Fig.5), it can be
226 concluded that weak electrical stimulation plays a selective driving role for autotrophic and
227 heterotrophic denitrifying bacteria. Under 0.2 V weak electrical stimulation, the genus
228 abundance of microbial communities in the EG group was significantly increased compared
229 to the CK group, especially *Thaurea* (8.2% and 10.4%), *Rhodocyclaceae* (8.0% and 9.1%),
230 *Denitratisoma* (3.1% and 3.4%), *Candidatus Competibacter* (1.3% and 1.5%), and other
231 microorganisms involved in the denitrification process. Most *Candidatus Competibacter* can
232 only undergo NO₃⁻-N reduction but not NO₂⁻-N reduction because they form NAR but not
233 NIR[28]. In contrast, *Thauera* was able to determine the reduction of NO₃⁻-N to nitrogen.
234 From this we speculate that it is the competition for electrons between various enzymes
235 during denitrification that affects N₂O accumulation[16],[29], causing both exogenous and
236 endogenous denitrification reactions in different situations. We then tested and analyzed the
237 enzyme activity and EPS of the different groups of sludge.

238 **3.3 Effect of enzyme activity on denitrification process**

239 The denitrification performance is related to the activity of four enzymes NAR, NIR,
240 NOR (nitric oxide reductase) and NOS[30], as expressed in formula (6)[31].

242 **Insert Fig.4 Weak electrically stimulated denitrification enzyme activity; (a)NAR**
243 **activity, (b) NIR activity**

244 The proceeding of denitrification depends to a large extent on the enzymatic activity,
245 which is significantly influenced by the relevant physicochemical factors. We examined and
246 analyzed the activity of two key enzymes (NAR and NIR) involved in the accumulation of
247 nitrite in sludge. Based on Fig.4, compared with the CK group, the activities of NAR and NIR
248 in the EG group were significantly enhanced by weak electrical stimulation at both 0.2 V and
249 0.4 V. Combined with the results in Fig.2, electrical stimulation can promote denitrification
250 by increasing the activity of NAR and NIR, which is one of the ways to improve NO_3^-
251 removal efficiency and reduce N_2O accumulation. NO_2^- -N is the product of the enzymatic
252 reaction of NAR, which in turn is promoted by NIR to reduce NO_2^- -N to N_2 . In other words,
253 an increase in NAR activity promotes the activity of NIR. The weak electrical stimulation
254 also optimized the microbial population structure (Fig.5). The proportion of heterotrophic
255 microorganisms such as *Saccharibacteria* and mutualistic microorganisms such as *Smithella*
256 decreased and the proportion of autotrophic microorganisms such as *Thauera* increased under
257 the weak electrical stimulation of 0.2V, which enhanced the autotrophic denitrification of
258 microorganisms.

259 The weak electrical stimulation at 0.6 V with low carbon source showed a slight

260 inhibition of NAR and NIR, which confirms that the lack of carbon source cannot be
261 remedied by increasing the voltage stimulation alone. At low C/ N ratios, insufficient electron
262 donors affect the ability of less competitive reductases such as NOR and NOS to compete for
263 electrons so that expressed genes related to denitrification are weakened. The carbon source
264 available was unable to synthesize sufficient denitrifying enzymes, which affected the growth
265 of the organism and the removal of nitrate and nitrite nitrogen. Denitrification enzymes
266 require a large number of electrons to operate in the reduction reaction. EPS can act as a
267 transient medium for electron energy transfer (EET) in activated sludge because of the
268 presence of large amounts of protein, which is closely related to the activity of NAR and NIR.

269 **Insert Fig.5 Level abundance of microbial population structure species under weak**
270 **electrical stimulation**

271 **3.4 Effect of extracellular polymers on denitrifying enzyme activity**

272 EPS played crucial roles in the ability of microorganisms to flocculate and in building
273 and maintaining biofilm structure. We carried out a qualitative and quantitative analysis of the
274 EPS from the three-dimensional fluorescence spectrogram (Fig.6). It can be observed that the
275 fluorescence intensity and area of fluorescence region I (Aromatic protein tyrosine) and II
276 (Aromatic protein tryptophan) of LB three-dimensional fluorescence spectrogram of the EG
277 group were higher than those of the CK group under the effect of weak electrical stimulation
278 of microorganisms, while the corresponding TB showed roughly the opposite trend. The
279 fluorescence intensities and areas of TB and LB in the EG and CK groups were in general
280 consistent with the trends of protein contents in the corresponding TB and LB. EPS played an
281 important role in enhancing intercellular communication as well as electron transfer[32].

282 Protein is the main component of EPS, in which aromatic protein-like substances have the
283 effect of accelerating electron transfer[33]. The increase of aromatic protein substances
284 promoted electron transfer between electroactive microorganisms and other microorganisms,
285 further enhancing denitrification efficiency.

286 **Insert Fig.6 EPS three-dimensional fluorescence spectrum of weak electrically**
287 **stimulated denitrification continuous flow experimental sludge**

288 The effect of weak electrical stimulation on EPS protein was not only in terms of
289 distribution, but also in terms of content. Fig.7 demonstrated that weak electrical stimulation
290 has a significant effect on the extracellular polymer. It is obvious that the sludge LB protein
291 content in the EG group was lower compared to the CK group, while the TB protein content
292 was higher than the CK group, with a tendency for the total EPS protein to increase. LB-EPS
293 was located in the outer layer, so the increase of its content can increase the zeta potential of
294 the cells and/or flocs. According to the DLVO theory, the electrostatic repulsion between the
295 cells and flocs increases, which hindered the flocculation effect and had an impact on SVI
296 (Sludge Volume Index). TB-EPS is located in the inner layer, which binds tightly to the cell
297 surface, stably adheres to the cell wall, and has little effect on the sludge[34]. The LB of the
298 EG group was much less than that of the CK group, which was consistent with the removal
299 performances of total nitrogen and nitrate nitrogen. With the decrease of LB, the degree of
300 sludge flocculation increases, and the adsorption and removal efficiency of pollutants was
301 better. When the intensity of weak electrical stimulation was 0.6 V, the protein content of LB
302 and TB in the EG group was lower than that of CK, and the total amount of EPS protein
303 decreased, which was obviously inhibited. It was speculated that the appropriate intensity of

304 weak electrical stimulation can transform EPS protein from LB to TB and increase the total
305 amount of EPS protein. Overall, weak electrical stimulation enhanced microbial metabolic
306 activity and protein secretion, and the appropriate intensity of weak electrical stimulation
307 enhanced microbial cell-to-cell communication and electron transfer by affecting the
308 distribution of LB and TB and the protein content in EPS.

309 **Insert Fig.7 EPS protein content of weak electrically stimulated denitrification**
310 **continuous flow experimental sludge. (a) COD:TN=3:1, (b) COD:TN=4:1**

311

312 **4. Conclusions**

313 Weak electrical stimulation has a selective effect on the dominant autotrophic
314 microorganisms and enhances denitrification of low carbon source wastewater through
315 enhanced autotrophic denitrification. Appropriate weak electrical stimulation effectively
316 enhanced denitrification by affecting the distribution and content of EPS aromatic proteins
317 with electron transfer function and the activity of denitrifying enzymes NAR and NIR, while
318 reducing the production of the intermediate greenhouse gas N_2O . The variation in gas
319 production showed that the various enzymatic activities responded differently to the weak
320 electrical stimuli and that when the microbial weak electrical stimuli were too intense, they
321 inhibited the enzymatic activity and thus affected the denitrification process. Weak
322 electrically stimulated denitrification is a process in which multiple microorganisms work in
323 concert. Based on the pattern of denitrifying enzyme effects, denitrification can be further
324 promoted in the future by detecting and regulating denitrifying bacteria.

325 **Acknowledgments**

326 The authors have stated that there was no conflict of interest. We gratefully
327 acknowledged the co-funding of this work by the National Natural Science Foundation of
328 China (No.52070130) and the Shuguang Project of Shanghai (Education and Scientific
329 Research Project of Shanghai,18SG45).

330 **References**

- 331 [1] C. Jiang, Q. Yang, D. Wang, Y. Zhong, F. Chen, X. Li, G. Zeng, X. Li, M. Shang,
332 Simultaneous perchlorate and nitrate removal coupled with electricity generation in
333 autotrophic denitrifying biocathode microbial fuel cell, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 308
334 (2017) 783-790.
- 335 [2] Y. Guo, Y. Peng, B. Wang, B. Li, M. Zhao, Achieving simultaneous nitrogen removal of
336 low C/N wastewater and external sludge reutilization in a sequencing batch reactor, *Chemical
337 Engineering Journal*, 306 (2016) 925-932.
- 338 [3] C. Ycab, Z.D. Rui, C. Qsa, C. Trab, C. Ywa, D. Xc, D. Jr, C. Dya, C. Mca, C.J.B.T. Twab,
339 Coupling anammox with denitrification in a full-scale combined biological nitrogen removal
340 process for swine wastewater treatment, *Bioresource Technology*, 329.
- 341 [4] F. Zhang, Z. He, Simultaneous nitrification and denitrification with electricity generation
342 in dual-cathode microbial fuel cells, *Journal of Chemical Technology & Biotechnology*, 87
343 (2012) 153-159.
- 344 [5] W. Li, S. Zhang, G. Chen, Y. Hua, Simultaneous electricity generation and pollutant
345 removal in microbial fuel cell with denitrifying biocathode over nitrite, *Applied Energy*, 126
346 (2014) 136-141.
- 347 [6] B. Virdis, K. Rabaey, R.A. Rozendal, Z. Yuan, J. Keller, Simultaneous nitrification,
348 denitrification and carbon removal in microbial fuel cells, *Water Research*, 44 (2010)
349 2970-2980.
- 350 [7] L. Jin, G. Zhang, H. Tian, Current state of sewage treatment in China, *Water Research*, 66
351 (2014) 85-98.
- 352 [8] Y. Zhang, I. Angelidaki, A new method for in situ nitrate removal from groundwater using
353 submerged microbial desalination-denitrification cell (SMDDC), *Water Research*, 47 (2013)
354 1827-1836.
- 355 [9] C.L. Chun, R.B. Payne, K.R. Sowers, H.D. May, Electrical stimulation of microbial PCB
356 degradation in sediment, *Water Research*, 47 (2013) 141-152.
- 357 [10] V. Beschkov, S. Velizarov, S.N. Agathos, V. Lukova, Bacterial denitrification of waste
358 water stimulated by constant electric field, *Biochemical Engineering Journal*, 17 (2004)
359 141-145.
- 360 [11] H. Liu, S. Tong, N. Chen, Y. Liu, C. Feng, Q. Hu, Effect of electro-stimulation on
361 activity of heterotrophic denitrifying bacteria and denitrification performance, *Bioresource*

362 Technology, 196 (2015) 123-128.

363 [12] B. Huang, H. Feng, Y. Ding, X. Zheng, M. Wang, N. Li, D. Shen, H. Zhang, Microbial
364 metabolism and activity in terms of nitrate removal in bioelectrochemical systems,
365 *Electrochimica Acta*, 113 (2013) 29-36.

366 [13] J.C. Thrash, J.D.J.E.S. Coates, *Technology, Review: Direct and Indirect Electrical*
367 *Stimulation of Microbial Metabolism, Environmental Science & Technology* ,42 (2008)
368 3921-3931.

369 [14] Z. Wang, C. Chen, H. Liu, D. Hrynshpan, T. Savitskaya, J. Chen, J. Chen, Effects of
370 carbon nanotube on denitrification performance of *Alcaligenes sp. TB*: Promotion of electron
371 generation, transportation and consumption,
372 *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 183 (2019) 109507.

373 [15] I. Verbaendert, N. Boon, P. De Vos, K. Heylen, Denitrification is a common feature
374 among members of the genus *Bacillus*, *Systematic and Applied Microbiology*, 34 (2011)
375 385-391.

376 [16] D.H. Pang, Z.F.J.P.C.T. Liu, *The Mechanism of Aerobic Denitrification and the Outlook*
377 *of Dealing with NO_x Waste Gas, Pollution Control Technology*, (2010).

378 [17] Gao, Y., Cornwell, C. J., Stoecker, K. D., Owens, S.J.B. M., Effects of
379 cyanobacterial-driven pH increases on sediment nutrient fluxes and coupled
380 nitrification-denitrification in a shallow fresh water estuary, *Biogeosciences*, (2012).

381 [18] H. Liu, F. Ouyang, Z. Chen, Z. Chen, E. Lichtfouse, Weak electricity stimulates
382 biological nitrate removal of wastewater: Hypothesis and first evidences, *Science of The Total*
383 *Environment*, 757 (2021) 143764.

384 [19] S. Wang, M. Gao, Z. Li, Z. She, J. Wu, D. Zheng, L. Guo, Y. Zhao, F. Gao, X. Wang,
385 Performance evaluation, microbial enzymatic activity and microbial community of a
386 sequencing batch reactor under long-term exposure to cerium dioxide nanoparticles,
387 *Bioresource Technology*, 220 (2016) 262-270.

388 [20] W. Chen, P. Westerhoff, J.A. Leenheer, K. Booksh, Fluorescence Excitation–Emission
389 Matrix Regional Integration to Quantify Spectra for Dissolved Organic Matter, *Environmental*
390 *Science & Technology*, 37 (2003) 5701-5710.

391 [21] M.M. Bradford, A rapid and sensitive method for the quantitation of microgram
392 quantities of protein utilizing the principle of protein-dye binding, *Analytical Biochemistry*,
393 72 (1976) 248-254.

394 [22] M. Prošňanský, T. Watanabe, M. Kuroda, Comparative study on the bio-electrochemical
395 denitrification equipped with a multi-electrode system, *Water Science and Technology*, 52
396 (2005) 479-485.

397 [23] P. Christensen, S. Rysgaard, N. Sloth, T. Dalsgaard, S.J.A.M.E. Schw?Rter, Sediment
398 mineralization, nutrient fluxes, denitrification and dissimilatory nitrate reduction to
399 ammonium in an estuarine fjord with sea cage trout farms, *Aquatic Microbial Ecology*, 257
400 (2000) 73-84.

401 [24] G. Wu, X. Zhai, C. Jiang, Y. Guan, Effect of ammonium on nitrous oxide emission
402 during denitrification with different electron donors, *Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 25
403 (2013) 1131-1138.

404 [25] Z. Hu, T. Lotti, M. van Loosdrecht, B. Kartal, Nitrogen removal with the anaerobic
405 ammonium oxidation process, *Biotechnology Letters*, 35 (2013) 1145-1154.

- 406 [26] K.Y. Park, Y. Inamori, M. Mizuochi, K.H. Ahn, Emission and control of nitrous oxide
 407 from a biological wastewater treatment system with intermittent aeration, *Journal of*
 408 *Bioscience Bioengineering*, 90 (2000) 247-252.
- 409 [27] Y. Zhou, M. Lim, S. Harjono, W.J. Ng, Nitrous oxide emission by denitrifying
 410 phosphorus removal culture using polyhydroxyalkanoates as carbon source, *Journal of*
 411 *Environmental Sciences*, 24 (2012) 1616-1623.
- 412 [28] A. Oehmen, G. Carvalho, C.M. Lopez-Vazquez, M.C.M. van Loosdrecht, M.A.M. Reis,
 413 Incorporating microbial ecology into the metabolic modelling of polyphosphate accumulating
 414 organisms and glycogen accumulating organisms, *Water Research*, 44 (2010) 4992-5004.
- 415 [29] Y. Pan, B.-J. Ni, P.L. Bond, L. Ye, Z. Yuan, Electron competition among nitrogen oxides
 416 reduction during methanol-utilizing denitrification in wastewater treatment, *Water Research*,
 417 47 (2013) 3273-3281.
- 418 [30] P.E. Hartzog, M. Sladek, J.J. Kelly, D.J. Larkin, Bottle effects alter taxonomic
 419 composition of wetland soil bacterial communities during the denitrification enzyme activity
 420 assay, *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 110 (2017) 87-94.
- 421 [31] X. Zheng, Y. Su, Y. Chen, R. Wan, M. Li, Y. Wei, H. Huang, Carboxyl-modified
 422 single-walled carbon nanotubes negatively affect bacterial growth and denitrification activity,
 423 *Sci Rep*, 4 (2014) 5653.
- 424 [32] Y. Xiao, E. Zhang, J. Zhang, Y. Dai, Z. Yang, H.E.M. Christensen, J. Ulstrup, F. Zhao,
 425 Extracellular polymeric substances are transient media for microbial extracellular electron
 426 transfer, *Science Advances*, 3 (2017) e1700623.
- 427 [33] C. Shih, A.K. Museth, M. Abrahamsson, A.M. Bianco-Rodriguez, A. Bilio, J. Sudhamsu,
 428 B.R. Crane, K.L. Ronayne, M. Towrie, A.V.J.S. Jr, Tryptophan-accelerated electron flow
 429 through proteins, *Science*, 320.
- 430 [34] G.-H. Yu, P.-J. He, L.-M. Shao, P.-P. He, Stratification Structure of Sludge Flocs with
 431 Implications to Dewaterability, *Environmental Science & Technology*, 42 (2008) 7944-7949.

432 **Figure Captions**

433 **Figure.1.** Continuous flow of weak electrically stimulated denitrification schematic diagram
 434 of the experimental setup

435 **Figure.2** Removal effect and pH change of weakly electrically stimulated denitrification
 436 continuous flow experiment;(a)TN, (b)NO₃⁻-N, (c) NO₂⁻-N, (d) NH₄⁺-N,(e)pH

437 **Figure.3** Denitrification gas production at optimal weak electrical stimulation intensity of 0.2
 438 V; (a) H₂, (b) N₂, (c) N₂O

439 **Figure.4** Weak electrically stimulated denitrification denitrifying enzyme activity; (a)NAR
 440 activity, (b) NIR activity

441 **Figure.5** Microbial population structure species level abundance under weak electrical

442 stimulation

443 **Figure.6** EPS three-dimensional fluorescence spectrum of weakly electrically stimulated

444 denitrification continuous flow experimental sludge

445 **Figure.7** EPS protein content of weak electrically stimulated denitrification continuous flow

446 experimental sludge. (a) COD:TN=3:1, (b) COD:TN=4:1

447

449 **Table 1. Composition of artificial simulated wastewater**

Ingredient	Concentration
$C_6H_{12}O_6$	0.0703g/L (C/N=3)
	0.0934g/L (C/N=4)
$C_2H_3NaO_2 \cdot 3H_2O$	0.1594g/L (C/N=3)
	0.2127g/L (C/N=4)
$NaNO_3$	0.3036g/L
KH_2PO_4	0.0099 g/L
$NaHCO_3$	0.1g/L
$CaCl_2$	0.01g/L
$MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$	0.1g/L
Trace elements	1 mL/L

451 **Table 2. Conditions for determination of hydrogen, nitrogen and nitrous oxide**

Composition	Detector	Temperature	Packed column	Inlet temperature	Column temperature	Carrier gas and velocity
H ₂	TCD	120°C	TDX-02, 2m*2mm	100°C	100°C	99.999%Ar, 30 ml/min
N ₂	TCD	200°C	SH-Rt®-Msieve 5A Capillary column, 30m*0.53mm*5 0µm	120°C	120°C	99.999%Ar, 1.5 ml/min
N ₂ O	µECD	100°C	Propack Q, 2m*2mm	100°C	70°C	99.999%Ar, 1.5 ml/min

452

453

454

455

456

457

458

Figure.1. Continuous flow of weak electrically stimulated denitrification schematic diagram of the experimental setup

Figure.2 Removal effect and pH change of weakly electrically stimulated denitrification continuous flow experiment;(a)TN, (b)NO₃--N, (c) NO₂--N, (d) NH₄+--N,(e)pH

Figure.4 Weak electrically stimulated denitrification denitrifying enzyme activity; (a)NAR activity, (b) NIR activity

[Click here to access/download;Figure;Fig.4.jpg](#)

A. *Saccharibacteria*; B. *Bacteroidetes vadinHA17*; C. *Flavobacterium*;

D. *Candidatus-competibacter*; E. *Parcubacteria*; F. *Fluviicola*;

G. *Anaerolineaceae*; H. *Smithella*; I. *Bacteria* clone OPB95; J. *Syntrophaceae*;

K. *Thauera*; L. *Rhodocyclaceae*; M. *Thiobacillus*; N. *PeM15*;

O. *Denitratisoma*; P. *Clostridium sensu stricto 1*; Q. *Sulfurisoma*

Figure.6 EPS three-dimensional fluorescence spectrum of weakly electrically stimulated denitrification continuous flow experimental sludge

[Click here to access/download;Figure;Fig.6.jpg](#)

Figure.7 EPS protein content of weak electrically stimulated denitrification continuous flow experimental sludge. (a) COD:TN=3:1, (b) COD:TN=4:1

[Click here to access/download;Figure;Fig.7.jpg](#)

[Click here to access/download](#)

Supplementary material for on-line publication only

Fig. S1.png

